

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Cumulative impact assessment of groundwater quality using water quality index, leachate pollution index, and GIS: A case study of Shivri Municipal Landfill Site, Lucknow, India

Vishvanath Pratap Singh *, Shashank Pandey and Vipin Kumar

Department of Civil Engineering, Institute of Engineering and Technology Lucknow, Lucknow – 226021, Uttar Pradesh, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(01), 1150–1159

Publication history: Received on 07 June 2024; revised on 12 July 2024; accepted on 15 July 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.1.2115>

Abstract

In the study, the groundwater quality near a dump in Lucknow City, Uttar Pradesh, India, is analyzed. To assess the quality of the groundwater and leachate close to the site, the leachate pollution index (LPI) and water quality index (WQI) have been calculated. Significant levels of contaminants were present at the dump site, as shown by the extremely high LPI score (28.45). 40% of the groundwater specimens are excellent, and 60% of the groundwater is in the good category, according to the WQI calculation for the groundwater samples and the map created for the WQI analysis that shows its regional distribution. The spatial distribution of WQI illustrates that the majority of the region around the site of the landfill is in the good category and the remaining is in the excellent category. The experimental result of the physicochemical analysis for groundwater revealed that water is satisfactory and fit for drinking and other domestic use and only some parameters like total alkalinity, total hardness, EC, TDS, sodium, magnesium, calcium, and sulfate are above the desirable limit set by Indian standard. In order to prevent and protect against the risk of groundwater contamination from leachate, this study also highlights the significance of LPI and WQI as monitoring tools for government agencies and policymakers.

Keywords: Leachate; Landfill; Groundwater; LPI; MSW; WQI

1. Introduction

Groundwater is one of the main sources of water for homes, businesses, and agriculture in many developing countries. One of the most alarming issues in recent years has been the contamination of groundwater by landfills. Landfills have detrimental effects on soil and air in addition to groundwater. The majority of these issues are brought on by poorly maintained or un-engineered landfills, which ultimately pose a danger of death, illness, and disability. These issues could also impede the advancement and expansion of the economy in a number of developing nations (Dermatas 2017). In many South Asian countries such as ours, groundwater resources have been overutilized by poor management and a lack of technical skills within government bodies. Today, engineered sanitary landfill sites are designed to protect groundwater from the various wastes disposed at the site. A study by Sharholi et al. 2008 suggests that about ninety percent of the total Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) produced in India is thrown away openly in a very unsanitary way. MSW management is a high-priority matter in various countries worldwide, including India. The waste management efforts are affected by limitations in landfill spaces, changes in legislation, climate, and social attitudes. According to a report by the Indian Infrastructure Report (IIR) and Central Pollution Control Board, India produces about 55 to 60 million tons of MSW annually which may rise to about 270 million tons in 2047.

MSW was approximately produced. The amount of collected solid waste was about 152750 tons per day (TPD) which was approximately 95% of the total MSW generated. Similarly, 79956 TPD solid wastes were treated, accounting for

* Corresponding author: Vishvanath Pratap Singh

about 50% of the total MSW generation. The amount of waste used for landfilling was about 29427 TPD which accounts for about 18% of the total MSW generated. Landfills have been observed to be the prime threats to groundwater which can be contaminated by either infiltration from precipitation or groundwater underflow (Mor et al. 2006). “Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2016” of the country guarantees proper gathering, segregation, transfer, treatment, and dumping of MSW while upgrading current facilities to prevent future pollution of groundwater and soil the scenario in recent times has changed in the sense that now the majority of the MSW is disposed-off on land in a controlled and scientific way. But still, there are places with poor disposal practices causing problems to the surrounding ecosystem and the health of people by being exposure to processes like consumption, inhalation in the shower, and dermal contact (Iwalewa and Makkawi 2015). A study conducted by Nandimandalam 2012 shows that if the pollutants that persist for a long time get into the groundwater, The water becomes unfit for human consumption. Physical and chemical factors, which are primarily influenced by geological processes and human activity, result in changes in the groundwater condition over an area. In order to properly manage MSW landfills and ultimately lessen groundwater contamination, the toxicity of landfill leachate should be evaluated.

Leachate pollution is often found within 7 km of the landfill's location, and substantial levels of pollution are reported around groundwater flow drift. (Abu-Rukah and Al-Kofahi 2001). Many studies suggest that landfill leachate may cause health problems by the process of solubilization and hydrolysis of MSW (Kale et al. 2010; Talalaj 2014; Singh et al. 2016; Chakraborty and Kumar 2016). Some studies suggest that heavy metals such as Fe, Pb, Zn, Cd, and Cr behave identically in leachate from landfills and groundwater nearby the site (Iwalewa and Makkawi 2015). Naveen et al. 2017 observed that heavy metals accumulated as traces of metals via the procedure of coprecipitation in the leachate pond mechanism and simply precipitation. Mishra et al. 2018 revealed the risks that are not cancer-causing for humans due to some chosen heavy metals out of MSW leachate from landfills. Pollutant leaching is increased by the direct dissolution of the waste by the colloid-facilitated mechanism of transport (State et al. 2013). These all facts prove that an environmentally friendly scientific approach should be adopted for continual monitoring of MSW.

leachate index is utilized mostly in locations with a high risk of leachate contamination to evaluate and track the possibility of leachate pollution. (Pratap Singh and Kumar Patel 2024). The leachate quality assessment by evaluation of LPI helps in (a) identifying the hazardous nature of leachate, (b) recognizing appropriate landfill structure, (c) developing ecologically sound treatment techniques, and (d) forecasting the impacts of leachate on surrounding groundwater through various investigation and monitoring methods (Sharma et al. 2008). The WQI is employed to evaluate the groundwater's suitability for consumption by humans lacking any harmful chemicals, that has been observed in samples of groundwater close to a landfill site (Talalaj 2014; Singh et al. 2015; Varol and Davraz 2015; Şener et al. 2017; Rabeiy 2018). A study by Deshmukh and Aher 2016 used spatial assessment through the application of the Inverse Distance Weight (IDW) in a Geographic Information System (GIS) for assessing groundwater near a landfill site and found that the groundwater was not fit for human consumption or domestic usage.

According to a 2015 report by the CPCB for 60 major Indian cities, uncollected garbage accounts for around 5% of the total MSW (1200 MT/day) generated, which is the primary cause of groundwater pollution in the city of Lucknow. This results in a significant volume of solid waste—roughly 60 MT of uncollected MSW per day. These solid wastes have the potential to significantly impact the atmosphere and subsurface water, particularly during the monsoon season. This investigation's goals are to evaluate the WQI for groundwater water quality and the LPI for leachate. It also uses the GIS technique to display the WQI results for the Shivri dump site in the city of Lucknow as a spatial distribution.

1.1. Study area description

Lucknow has become one of the places in India where advancement happens at an explosive rate. It also serves as the capital of the state city as well as among the most extremely inhabited states in India. This city lies in the northern hemisphere with a longitudinal extent of 80.30 degrees east to 81.13 degrees east and a latitudinal extent of 26.30 degrees north to 28.45 degrees north. The environment of Lucknow is constantly exacerbated by the unprecedented need for land, water, public transportation, education, healthcare centers, housing, and various other means, which has grown due to the explosive increase in urban development. Over the entire region, the average elevation is around 123 meters above mean sea level. This location lies in the center of the region known as northern India. It takes up land beside the Gomti rivers, which run across the city.

the city of Lucknow tends to be marked by moderate dry conditions across the entire year except for Rainy weather conditions. The region also receives substantial precipitation primarily throughout the monsoon period with an annual average precipitation of around 827.2 mm. The overall extent of the water level alternates from 1-15.78 m in Lucknow city beneath ground level.

the city of Lucknow city possesses an approximate population of 38,00,000, which is expected to culminate in approximately two thousand metric tons of waste every day. A typical individual produces a quantity of solid waste between 100 to 650 g in the city, which relies on the socioeconomic status of individuals inhabiting it. The MSW produced in city areas may be classified into bio-medical, commercial, and domestic garbage. The amount of waste produced in rural regions is between 0.65-0.45 kg/capita/day.

A landfill located near Shivri began operating in the city of Lucknow in 2007 at an estimated separation of roughly 25 kilometers from the city. The waste site was suggested for being a designed and adequately lined site yet under construction up to 2024 at the moment when I began drafting this current paper.

1.2. Shivri landfill site, Lucknow

Established in 2007, the Shivri landfill plant has remained operational. It has a location in the western section of the city and spans an area of roughly 41 hectares. The site is still under construction as I write this paper. 1200 T/day of trash is usually deposited at the site, which is spread out over the region and varies in height from 15 to 22 meters. Household debris from all across the Lucknow region, including plastics, glass, paper, and glassware, as well as kitchen waste, clothing, and cardboard containers, makes up the majority of the rubbish dumped at this landfill. Moreover, this location also handles the disposal of garbage from the adjacent fish market, plant market, and slaughterhouse. The waste disposal site is an adequately designed dumping zone that reaches a height of 15 to 22 meters, giving the impression that it is a huge mound of garbage. The garbage from municipalities is transported to this site by trucks as well as other means of transportation from different locations of the city and dumped here. They also operate a recycling facility where they frequently gather glass items, metal, and plastic to ship for other uses. Our investigation aims to comprehend how the amount of moisture in the garbage gathered in this location leads to the production of leachate.

2. Material and method

2.1. Sampling and testing of Leachate and groundwater

Leachate samples were collected from the landfill site's drainage system using sterile, airtight plastic bottles. Similarly, five handpumps at the Shivri waste site were cleaned and throwaway bottles were washed in an improper manner in order to extract groundwater samples. A differential global positioning system (DGPS) was used to get the precise sampling locations, which were subsequently used to map the research region. At the Environmental lab of the Department of Civil Engineering, IET Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India, the critical physical and chemical variables were evaluated for the leachate and groundwater samples using established procedures and techniques. The separation distance of the locations for sampling of groundwater from the landfill site ranges from 188 to 973 m. Total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, Total alkalinity, total hardness (TH) Electrical conductivity (EC), Calcium, sodium, magnesium, fluoride, sulfate, and boron belong to the chemical and physical characteristics examined in groundwater samples. An SCM was applied to measure pH and electrical conductivity. The parameters which are included in the leachate sample were TSS, phosphate, BOD, COD, NO₃, NH₃, and Cd. Total alkalinity (TA), TH, and chloride in the specimen of groundwater were obtained by titrimetry. Flame AAS 4141 instrument (Electronic Corporation of India Limited) and inductively coupled plasma-mass-spectrometry (ICP-MS) were applied to know the heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cr, Fe, and Cd) content. Digestion of a 50 ml sample in 10 ml of concentrated HNO₃ till the solution becomes transparent was done to estimate heavy metals in leachate samples. Flame photometry was employed for the assessment of K, Na, and Ca in the samples of groundwater. UV-spectrophotometer (Systronics) was used for the determination of nitrate using the colorimetric method. An ion-selective electrode (ISE) meter was employed for the determination of fluoride content in the samples of groundwater. The weight arithmetic method was used for the evaluation of WQI and LPI which will help identify water resource status (Tyagi et al. 2014; Balathandayutham et al. 2015; Chakraborty and Kumar 2016).

2.2. LPI calculation of the landfill site

The following formula, which is based on the Rand Corporation Delphi technique, was used to determine the leachate's LPI in order to evaluate the polluting potential of the material at the Shivri landfill site.

$$LPI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m w_i p_i}{\sum w_i} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where m denotes the total number of known concentrations of leachate variables, w_i is used for the weight factor i th contaminant parameter, and p_i is used for the sub-index score of i th contaminant parameter. Each pollutant's level of significance has been taken into account while determining the weights for all 13 parameters. Averaged sub-index curves were used to obtain the calculation of sub-index values as suggested by (Kumar and Alappat 2005). Sub-index

curves denote the relationship between the considered pollutant concentration and leachate contamination. The calculation of cumulative pollution rating (*wi pi*) is done by the multiplication of the weight factor and sub-index value. The weight factor gives specification about the significance of the contaminating parameter about the overall leachate contamination. Lastly, the cumulative contamination ratings of all metrics are added up to determine the landfill leachate LPI.

2.3. WQI calculation

The WQI, which aids in determining the status of water resources, was calculated using the weight arithmetic method. (Chakraborty and Kumar 2016). The calculation of the WQI for all the groundwater samples was done employing the weighted arithmetic index method (Kumari and Sharma 2019). The WQI value and the water quality status are given in Table 1.

$$WQI = \Sigma(qn \times wn) / \Sigma wn \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

First of all, the unit weight (*wn*) was calculated for every variable by applying the following equation

$$wn = K / Sn \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

wn = Unit weight of *n*th parameters
Sn = Standard desirable value
K = proportionality Constant

$$K = [1 / (\Sigma(1 / Sn))] \dots\dots (4)$$

$$qn = (Vn / Sn) \times 100 \dots\dots (5)$$

Where, *Vn* = measured value of the *n*th variable, *qn* = Sub-index value.

Table 1 WQI values and their water quality status

S.No.	Range of WQI values	Category
1	0 to 25	Excellent
2	26 to 50	Good
3	51 to 75	Fair
4	76 to 100	Poor
5	101 to 150	Very poor
6	Above 150	Unfit for drinking

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Calculation of LPI for Shivri landfill leachate

Estimation of LPI for the Shivri landfill site was done using pollution concentration, weight factor, and sub-index value of 13 significant LPI variables as given in **Table 2**.

The Shivri dump site's LPI, which is relatively high, was found to be 28.45. It will be harmful to the environment and human health if the LPI score is higher than 7.50. Since the LPI score was significantly greater than 7.50, the landfill site's environmental condition can be deemed hazardous and non-stabilized. Therefore, it will be dangerous if the landfill leachate gets into the groundwater. The elevated LPI value was caused by an excess of BOD, COD, and TSS. An important consideration for permitting disposal in many nations is the TSS value, which was found to be 132.8 mg/l, above the leachate disposal standard of 100 mg/l (Koshy et al. 2008).

Table 2 LPI of Shivri landfill leachate

Parameters	Weight factor (w_i)	Pollutant concentration	Sub-index value (p_i)	Cumulative pollution rating ($w_i \times p_i$)
pH	0.009	7.89	87.66	0.759
TSS	0.001	132.8	13.28	0.010
PO ₄	0.016	1.55	31	0.484
F	0.039	1.56	78	3.042
Fe	0.026	0.65	21.66	0.56
Zn	0.016	0.34	6.8	0.106
Pb	0.78	0.01	10	7.8
Cd	0.039	0.08	4	0.156
Cr	0.039	0.41	20.5	0.799
BOD	0.003	100.1	333	11.1
COD	0.001	500.3	200	0.062
NO ₃	0.008	12.2	122	0.952
NH ₃	0.016	1.33	26.6	0.41

Note - Except for pH, all values are in mg/l.

$$LPI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m w_i p_i}{\sum w_i}$$

$$LPI = 27.71/0.97$$

$$LPI = 28.45$$

BOD concentration was found to be 100 mg/l which was again higher than the prescribed limit for inland water discharge (30 mg/l). This shows that there was high organic pollution in the leachate sample. The concentration of COD was observed to be 500 mg/l which was two times the permissible standard for inland water discharge of 250 mg/l. there was a notable amount of heavy metal presence observed in the shape of Fe (0.65 mg/l), Zn (0.34 mg/l), Cd (0.08 mg/l), and total chromium (0.41 mg/l). the presence of heavy metals plays an essential part in the detrimental effects because of their lasting persistent and reducing properties in the surroundings. However, the simplification of the concentration variation of leachate contamination in particular periods is very difficult, and in the majority of instances, the increase observed was within a very short period (Abdelaal et al. 2014).

3.2. Groundwater quality statistical analysis for physicochemical parameters

Statistical analysis of groundwater quality for physicochemical variables in terms of standard deviation, the maximum, minimum, and mean concentration is given in Table 3 the pH of the sample varies from 7.18 to 7.55 with an overall mean of 7.344. the standard deviation for the given samples was found to be 0.14. the slightly basic nature of the samples can be due to the presence of bicarbonates (Adams et al. 2001). The value of the electrical conductivity (EC) fluctuates from 656 μ S/cm to 885 μ S/cm alongside a mean of 775.2 μ S/cm for all the groundwater samples. The observed standard deviation value for EC was 77.90 μ S/cm for all the groundwater samples. The amount of TDS varies from 505 to 566.4 mg/l alongside a mean of 524.46 mg/l. standard deviation for TDS values was 21.82 mg/l. at some groundwater sampling locations, elevated values for EC and TDS can be caused by landfill waste leaching near the sampling locations. The alkalinity was observed to have levels ranging from 220.4 to 254.1 mg/l. Mean alkalinity and its standard deviation were found to be 239.792 and 12.52 respectively. The hardness value fluctuates from 219.36 mg/l to 242.36 mg/l with a mean of 232.488 mg/l. the standard deviation value for the hardness of the samples of groundwater was found to be 9.41. The weathering of silicate in the dry season and wet season may be responsible for the high hardness values (Nandimandalam 2012; Varol and Davraz 2014).

Table 3 Statistical evaluation of physicochemical properties of samples of groundwater

Parameters	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation	Guideline for drinking water (BIS-10500:2012)
pH	7.18	7.55	7.344	0.13	7.5
EC	656	885	775.2	77.90	500
TDS	505	566.4	524.46	21.82	500
Total alkalinity	220.4	254.1	239.792	12.52	200
Hardness	219.36	242.36	232.488	9.40	200
Ca	79.21	97.33	87.71	6.62	75
Mg	34.62	49.09	42.546	5.26	30
Na	205.36	253.13	234.234	18.54	200
Sulphate	213.21	243.01	232.966	10.74	200
Cl	248.19	259.1	254.398	3.66	250
F	0.19	0.44	0.334	0.10	1
B	0.1	0.6	0.38	0.17	0.5
Fe	0.09	0.13	0.108	0.01	0.3
Zn	0.09	0.18	0.13	0.03	5
Pb	0.002	0.004	0.0028	0.0007	0.01
Cr	0.001	0.003	0.0024	0.0008	0.05

Note - Except for pH and EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), all parameter values are expressed in mg/l.

The chloride values obtained for the samples of groundwater range from 231.56 to 248.19 mg/l the mean value for these obtained samples was 240.008 mg/l and it had a standard deviation of 5.57. all the chloride values were found to be under the prescribed limit of Indian standards. The mean values obtained for Na, Mg, and Ca were found to be 234.324 mg/l, 42.546 mg/l, and 87.71 mg/l respectively. The fluoride values fluctuate from 0.19 to 0.44 mg/l with an average of 0.33 mg/l and standard deviation of 0.10. low fluoride concentration indicates a controlled lithogenic impact in a groundwater sample. This may also indicate the non-availability of fluoride-bearing minerals in the study area (Janardhana Raju et al. 2011). The iron concentration of the samples of groundwater was found to have an average of 0.108 mg/l and a standard deviation of 0.015. The Domestic wastes that consist of iron-containing steel may be responsible for the iron concentration observed in the groundwater samples (Nagarajan et al. 2012). The other explanation that may be given for the presence of iron in groundwater is the reduction of ferric ions into ferrous ions by the weather materials (Raju 2006). The higher consumption of water containing iron may cause a disease named hemosiderosis (Rajappa et al. 2010). The observed chromium concentration was observed to have an average of 0.0024 mg/l with a standard deviation of 0.0008. these characteristics of the samples show that the hardness, alkalinity, and sodium concentrations were found to be more than the desirable limit set by BIS.

3.3. Using WQI for the evaluation of the quality of groundwater close to the landfill site

The experimental results obtained for all 5 samples of groundwater were used for the evaluation of WQI. The Indian standards and WHO standards were put into use for the calculation of WQI as shown in **Table 4** and **Table 5**. As per the calculated WQI value, the water quality may be divided into 6 categories, i.e., Excellent, good, fair, poor, very poor, and not fit for drinking. The range of the WQI values calculated was from 18.04 to 34.23 at all the sampling locations. Two samples; sample 4 and sample 5 with WQI values of 18.04 and 18.11 respectively were in the excellent category the other 3 samples; samples 1, 2, and 3 with WQI values of 34.23, 26.42, and 26.88 respectively were in the good category. the results obtained for the samples show that 60% of the samples were in the good category and 40% were in the excellent category. So, the result suggests that the groundwater close to the landfill was not much affected by its presence.

Table 4 Weighting of the parameters related to water quality³

Parameters	WHO standards (2011) (mg/l)	BIS standards (2012) (mg/l)	Relative weight (wn)
pH	6.5-8.5	7.5	0.0010604
EC	-	500	0.00001591
TDS	500	500	0.00001591
Total alkalinity	-	200	0.00003976
Hardness	-	200	0.00003976
Ca	300	75	0.000106
Mg	-	30	0.0002651
Na	200	200	0.00003976
Sulphate	-	200	0.00003976
Cl	250	250	0.00003181
F	1.3	1	0.0079528
B	1	0.5	0.0079528
Fe	0.3	0.3	0.0265094
Zn	-	5	0.0015906
Pb	-	0.01	0.7952834
Cr	0.05	0.05	0.1590567

Table 5 WQI values and water type for groundwater samples

Location	Sample	WQI	Water type
Near Gate No. 2 (188 m)	W1	34.23	Good
Shivri Village Road (360 m)	W2	26.42	Good
Near residential area (524 m)	W3	26.87	Good
Near Mohan Road (863 m)	W4	18.04	Excellent
Near Mohan Road (973 m)	W5	18.12	Excellent

3.4. WQI Spatial distribution

IDW for interpolation in ArcGIS was used to map the study area's spatial distribution (Figure 1). In order to distinguish between the samples' excellent and good classifications, the third class in the geographical distribution map was manually placed at 25. The distribution clearly shows that three samples were in excellent and two were in good category. It can be interpreted from the mapping that most of the area was in an excellent category and only a small portion near the landfill site was in good category. Although there was not much impact found on the groundwater but still the groundwater near the landfill site was somewhat poorer than the groundwater away from the site.

Figure 1 Spatial distribution map for the WQI

4. Conclusion

The physicochemical characteristics of the groundwater close to the Shivri landfill site in Lucknow were examined. Since the groundwater from the handpumps close to the dump is the main source of drinking water for the local families, it was tested. Based on the findings of this investigation, we may conclude that the water was fit for drinking and household purposes even though a minor fluctuation was observed from the desirable limit for some of its parameters like EC, TDS, TA, Hardness, Ca, Mg, Na, and SO₄. A high value (28.45) of LPI shows that the landfill leachate has a substantial proportion of pollutant presence. The WQI results indicate that 40% of the samples of groundwater were in the excellent category and 60% of the specimens were in the good category. Due to an effective collection system in place, the WQI spatial distribution shows that the dump site had no negative effects on the bulk of the area surrounding it. This study demonstrates that the existence of the Shivri landfill site has had no impact on the quality of the groundwater nearby.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The Institute of Engineering and Technology Lucknow's Department of Civil Engineering is acknowledged by the authors for providing the resources needed to carry out the study.

Authors Contributions

Vishvanath Pratap Singh: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Validation. Shashank Pandey: Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. Vipin Kumar: Writing & Editing.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The writers clearly state that they do not have any contradictory agendas.

References

- [1] Abdelaal FB, Rowe RK, Islam MZ (2014) Effect of leachate composition on the long-term performance of a HDPE geomembrane. *Geotextiles and Geomembranes* 42:348–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOTEXMEM.2014.06.001>
- [2] Abu-Rukah Y, Al-Kofahi O (2001) The assessment of the effect of landfill leachate on ground-water quality—a case study. El-Akader landfill site—north Jordan. *J Arid Environ* 49:615–630. <https://doi.org/10.1006/JARE.2001.0796>
- [3] Adams S, Titus R, Pietersen K, et al (2001) Hydrochemical characteristics of aquifers near Sutherland in the Western Karoo, South Africa. *J Hydrol (Amst)* 241:91–103. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(00\)00370-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(00)00370-X)
- [4] Balathandayutham K, Mayilswami C, Tamilmani D (2015) Assessment of Groundwater Quality using GIS: A Case Study of Walayar Watershed, Parambikulam-Aliyar-Palar Basin, Tamilnadu, India. *Current World Environment* 10:602–609. <https://doi.org/10.12944/cwe.10.2.25>
- [5] Chakraborty S, Kumar RN (2016) Assessment of groundwater quality at a MSW landfill site using standard and AHP based water quality index: a case study from Ranchi, Jharkhand, India. *Environ Monit Assess* 188:335. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-016-5336-x>
- [6] Dermatas D (2017) Waste management and research and the sustainable development goals: Focus on soil and groundwater pollution. *Waste Management and Research* 35:453–455
- [7] Deshmukh KK, Aher SP (2016) Assessment of the Impact of Municipal Solid Waste on Groundwater Quality near the Sangamner City using GIS Approach. *Water Resources Management* 30:2425–2443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-016-1299-5>
- [8] Iwalewa TM, Makkawi MH (2015) Site characterization and risk assessment in support of the design of groundwater remediation well near a hazardous landfill. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 8:1705–1715. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-014-1300-7>
- [9] Janardhana Raju N, Shukla UK, Ram P (2011) Hydrogeochemistry for the assessment of groundwater quality in Varanasi: a fast-urbanizing center in Uttar Pradesh, India. *Environ Monit Assess* 173:279–300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-010-1387-6>
- [10] Kale SS, Kadam AK, Kumar S, Pawar NJ (2010) Evaluating pollution potential of leachate from landfill site, from the Pune metropolitan city and its impact on shallow basaltic aquifers. *Environ Monit Assess* 162:327–346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-009-0799-7>
- [11] Koshy L, Jones T, Bérubé K (2008) Bioreactivity of municipal solid waste landfill leachates—Hormesis and DNA damage. *Water Res* 42:2177–2183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WATRES.2007.11.030>
- [12] Kumar D, Alappat BJ (2005) Analysis of leachate pollution index and formulation of sub-leachate pollution indices. *Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy* 23:230–239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X05054875>
- [13] Kumari R, Sharma RC (2019) Assessment of water quality index and multivariate analysis of high altitude sacred Lake Prashar, Himachal Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 16:6125–6134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-018-2007-1>
- [14] Mishra H, Karmakar S, Kumar R, Kadambala P (2018) A long-term comparative assessment of human health risk to leachate-contaminated groundwater from heavy metal with different liner systems. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 25:2911–2923. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-0717-4>
- [15] Mor S, Ravindra K, Dahiya RP, Chandra A (2006) Leachate Characterization and Assessment of Groundwater Pollution Near Municipal Solid Waste Landfill Site. *Environ Monit Assess* 118:435–456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-006-1505-7>
- [16] Nagarajan R, Thirumalaisamy S, Lakshumanan E (2012) Impact of leachate on groundwater pollution due to non-engineered municipal solid waste landfill sites of erode city, Tamil Nadu, India. *Iranian J Environ Health Sci Eng* 9:35. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1735-2746-9-35>
- [17] Nandimandalam JR (2012) Evaluation of hydrogeochemical processes in the Pleistocene aquifers of Middle Ganga Plain, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Environ Earth Sci* 65:1291–1308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-011-1377-1>

- [18] Naveen BP, Mahapatra DM, Sitharam TG, et al (2017) Physico-chemical and biological characterization of urban municipal landfill leachate. *Environmental Pollution* 220:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2016.09.002>
- [19] Pratap Singh V, Kumar Patel P (2024) Characterization of Leachate and assessment of groundwater contamination near Shivri landll site, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh (India). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4483983/v1>
- [20] Rabeiy RE (2018) Assessment and modeling of groundwater quality using WQI and GIS in Upper Egypt area. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 25:30808–30817. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-8617-1>
- [21] Rajappa B, Manjappa S, Puttaiah ET (2010) Monitoring of Heavy Metal Concentration in Groundwater of Hakinaka Taluk, India
- [22] Raju NJ (2006) Iron contamination in groundwater: A case from Tirumala-Tirupati environs, India
- [23] Şener Ş, Şener E, Davraz A (2017) Evaluation of water quality using water quality index (WQI) method and GIS in Aksu River (SW-Turkey). *Science of The Total Environment* 584–585:131–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2017.01.102>
- [24] Sharholly M, Ahmad K, Mahmood G, Trivedi RC (2008) Municipal solid waste management in Indian cities – A review. *Waste Management* 28:459–467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2007.02.008>
- [25] Sharma A, Meesa S, Pant S, et al (2008) Formulation of a landfill pollution potential index to compare pollution potential of uncontrolled landfills. *Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy* 26:474–483. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X07086515>
- [26] Singh S, Raju NJ, Gossel W, Wycisk P (2016) Assessment of pollution potential of leachate from the municipal solid waste disposal site and its impact on groundwater quality, Varanasi environs, India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 9:131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-015-2131-x>
- [27] Singh S, Raju NJ, Ramakrishna Ch (2015) Evaluation of Groundwater Quality and Its Suitability for Domestic and Irrigation Use in Parts of the Chandauli-Varanasi Region, Uttar Pradesh, India. *J Water Resour Prot* 07:572–587. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jwarp.2015.77046>
- [28] State W, Chatterjee N, Flury M, et al (2013) Chemical and Physical Characteristics of Compost Leachates-A Review-Report prepared for the
- [29] Talalaj IA (2014) Assessment of groundwater quality near the landfill site using the modified water quality index. *Environ Monit Assess* 186:3673–3683. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-3649-1>
- [30] Tyagi S, Singh P, Sharma B, Singh R (2014) Assessment of Water Quality for Drinking Purpose in District Pauri of Uttarakhand, India. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Sciences* 2:94–99. <https://doi.org/10.12691/aees-2-4-2>
- [31] Varol S, Davraz A (2015) Evaluation of the groundwater quality with WQI (Water Quality Index) and multivariate analysis: a case study of the Tefenni plain (Burdur/Turkey). *Environ Earth Sci* 73:1725–1744. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-014-3531-z>
- [32] Varol S, Davraz A (2014) Assessment of geochemistry and hydrogeochemical processes in groundwater of the Tefenni plain (Burdur/Turkey). *Environ Earth Sci* 71:4657–4673. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-013-2856-3>